

Klimatise:

Tackling buildings' energy waste
with AI-driven comfort control

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BridgeAI

CASE STUDY

klimate

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Non-domestic buildings account for more than 10% of global CO2 emissions. And, in the UK, around 70% of our built environment's carbon footprint comes from operational processes such as heating and cooling. [Klimate](#) was created to tackle that problem. The UK-based company is developing an AI-powered system to optimise heating, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) in commercial buildings, reducing carbon emissions while keeping occupants comfortable.

The software integrates into existing building management systems, automatically adjusting temperature points each day to balance comfort and efficiency. Early pilots have shown savings of up to 30% in heating and cooling loads – even in new, supposedly efficient buildings.

From the outset, Klimate planned to adopt AI into its climate-control platform. The approach would combine sensor data with feedback from occupants, who could report how they feel via a simple web app. Machine learning models would then analyse this data to identify problem zones – for example, a meeting room that consistently feels too cold – and recommend targeted temperature adjustments.

“It’s the middle of summer but you have to keep a jumper on the back of your chair because it gets so cold in the office. Lots of us know that situation,” says Vic Tink, founder of climate tech startup Klimate. “But it’s not just about our own comfort – it’s a signal that the building isn’t running efficiently.”

Vic Tink, co-founder and Chief Technology Officer, Klimate

But like many early-stage companies, Klimatise lacked the in-house expertise to capitalise on the potential of AI. Participation in Innovate UK BridgeAI's Independent Scientific Advisor (ISA) offer made the difference. Matched with ISA Dr Ogerta Elezaj, Turing Fellow at The Alan Turing Institute and Associate Professor in Applied AI at Birmingham City University, the company received both strategic guidance and hands-on technical support. Ogerta also involved one of her students in the MSc Artificial Intelligence programme at Birmingham City University, Madiba Okolo, who contributed a major component of the product as part of his dissertation.

Together, they built a prototype multi-modal AI framework that combines sensor readings and occupant feedback to optimise zone-specific temperatures. Madiba developed a machine vision tool to automatically zone building floorplans too. Vic says: "Before this project, our system was good at adjusting overall temperature setpoints, but it didn't know where in the building the problems were. Now we can identify specific hot and cold spots, which makes our solution far more powerful. It's an entire new feature that we couldn't have built in-house right now."

"Working with Ogerta and Madiba has been a huge boost. They've helped us solve problems we simply couldn't tackle on our own, and given us a whole new feature to take to market. Just as importantly, they've been a trusted sounding board as we make decisions about our product and our business. The BridgeAI ISA offer has made a massive difference."

Vic Tink, co-founder and Chief Technology Officer, Klimatise

Credit: klimatise.com

Ogerta describes the project as a strong example of bridging academia and industry: “The company had a clear vision but needed help to implement it. By guiding their AI adoption work and bringing an enthusiastic master’s student into the project, we were able to deliver a working prototype, not just concepts. That gives Klimatise something tangible to show potential clients, while also offering a talented student valuable real-world experience.”

Looking ahead, Klimatise has several customers waiting for full deployment of its software in large office buildings. With a functioning prototype in place, the team is now focused on integrating the new AI features, scaling its solution, and onboarding more clients.

Vic Tink, co-founder and Chief Technology Officer, Klimatise

About Innovate UK BridgeAI

Innovate UK BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. We bridge the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency and data privacy, we aim to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

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